

A Market Research on Current Energy Metering System and Future Opportunities

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Abstract

Energy meter is an important device that is used to measure power. It is almost used everywhere like houses, industries, factories etc., to know about their power consumption. Over a decade many modifications and developments has been taken place in the construction and operation of the energy meters. From the above, this paper presents the development of various energy meters and their applications. Different types of energy meters along with the innovation in this field are being discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Energy meters, power consumption, digital electronic energy meters.

1. Introduction

Energy meter is an instrument which measures the amount of electrical energy used by the consumers everyday. Utilities install these type of instruments everywhere like houses, industries, organizations etc. to charge the electricity used by many types of loads. These meters measure the instantaneous voltages and currents and calculates the instantaneous power by their product. This power is integrated over certain time period which gives the energy utilized or consumed over that time period. These may be single phase meters or three phase meters depending on the power utilized by domestic or commercial installations [1]. For small loads like domestic purposes, these meters can be directly connected between the line and the load. But for larger loads used in industries, step down current transformers must be placed to prevent the energy meters from higher currents. As the demand of the electricity is increasing day by day and therefore the utilization of the new and more advanced energy meters have increased. The paper provides a brief idea of the energy meters, their architecture, types and their working. It also focuses on the recent advances and developments related to energy meters [3].

2. Literature Review

The recent developments in smart metering systems have led to the construction and development of a new type of energy meter, that are operated on the basis of event-driven principles [2]. The event-driven metering concepts are applied to represent the information on the electrical load patterns, which will have an integral value. This paper explains, why these concepts are different from the ones used for event-based applications in other domains, discusses the principles used in the new types of electricity meter, also presents the data format structured in such a way to provide detailed knowledge about the representation, and shows the results on real-time applications. In order to represent the effectiveness of the event-driven metering scheme, a specific index is defined that is illustrated to represent the details of the metering pattern and comparing the results with the standards which occur in most favourable cases through regular timer-driven metering. The most important advantage of event-driven metering system over the traditional time driven system is that it gives both specific and distinct applications based on the real life data sets [4]. The authors has proposed, designed and implemented a Universal Smart Energy Meter (USEM) with demand-side load management at low cost. There exist flexible tariff plans like time of use, block rate tariff or both for which the meter can be used in both prepaid and post-paid modes[5]. The smart meter consists of potential transformer, current transformer, and microcontroller unit with an embedded communication module [6]. The connectivity among the utility, the smart meter and consumer is established by an authority identification number, meter identification number, and user identification number. By using cellular network one can access it. The digital implementation of Fast Discrete Stockwell Transform (FDST) with automatic scaling is also introduced which is used for accurate PQ-event detection (ED) and energy metering [7]. The comparative analysis of FDSTbased energy-metering algorithm is carried out with existing algorithms like fast Fourier transform and filter-based design. The results demonstrate that the FDSTbased energy-metering algorithm exceeds the existing algorithms in many ways like in accuracy, complexity and adaptability under PQ events [8]. The easy development of new applications making costand timeeffective, in migration to future smart grid infrastructures and simple adjustments to change in the

relevant standards is one of its advantages. The development of the induction-type energy meter is discussed. The measurement equipment for the calibration of energy meters is also explained. Its structure and metrological characterization are discussed [10]. Two online digital compensation procedures have been realized and are shown to improve its performances without increasing its costs: one increases the spectral purity of test signals and the other corrects the transducer frequency response. Experimental results that are related to metrological characterization have shown that the realized calibrator is suitable for the onsite calibration of energy meters.

3. Architecture of Energy Meter

The energy meter has four main parts. They are the Driving System, Moving System, Braking System and Registering System [1].

3.1 Driving System

The electromagnet is the main component of the driving system. It is the temporary magnet which gets excited by the flow of current through a coil. The core of the electromagnet is made up of silicon steel lamination. The driving system has two electromagnets. The upper part is called as shunt electromagnet, and the lower part is called as series electromagnet.

The series electromagnet is excited by the flow of load current through the current coil. The coil of the shunt electromagnet is called as pressure coil and is directly connected with the supply. Hence it carries the current proportional to the shunt voltage. The centre limb of the magnet consists of copper band which are adjustable. The function of the copper band is to align the flux produced by the shunt magnet in proportional with the supplied voltage.

3.2 Moving System

The moving system is an aluminium disc that is mounted on the shaft of the alloy. The disc is inserted between the air gap of the two electromagnets. Due to the change in magnetic field, an eddy current is induced which is cut by the magnetic flux. A deflecting torque is induced when there is an interaction of flux and disc. The aluminium disc starts rotating when the devices consume power. Depending upon the number of rotations made by the aluminium disc the total load is displayed in terms of units or kwh in a certain interval of time period.

3.3 Braking system

A permanent magnet is used for reducing the number of rotations made by the disc as it induces eddy currents. The magnetic flux produced by the permanent magnet is cut by the eddy current produced and hence the braking torque is induced. The braking torque reduces the speed by opposing the movement of the disc. The braking torque is adjustable as alike the permanent magnet by shifting the magnet to other positions radially.

3.4 Registration (Counting Mechanism)

The number of rotations of the aluminium disc are recorded by the registration mechanism. Their rotation is directly proportional to the energy consumed by the loads in the kilowatt hour. The rotation of the disc is transmitted to the pointers of the different dial for recording the different readings. The multiplication of the number of rotations of the disc with the meter constant give the total number of power consumed in units or kwh.

4. Working of Energy Meter

The energy meter has an aluminium disc placed between the air gap of series and shunt electro magnet, whose rotations determines the power consumption of the load. The shunt magnet consists of pressure coil, and the series magnet consists of current coil. Due to the supply voltage, the pressure coil creates the magnetic field and the current coil produces current. The field induced by the voltage coil is lagging by 90° on the magnetic field of the current coil and due to which eddy current is induced in the disc. The interaction of the eddy current and the magnetic field induces torque which exerts a force on the disc that makes the disc rotating. The force on the disc is directly proportional to the current and voltage of the coil induced. The

permanent magnet controls their rotation by opposing the movement of the disc. The cyclometer counts the rotation of the disc.

Figure 1. Construction of Energy meter

5. Different Types of Energy Meters

Energy meter also known as watt hour meter, is classified based on several factors like 1) Type of display like analog meter and digital meter, 2) Type of metering point used like grid or primary, secondary and local distribution. 3) End applications like domestic, commercial and industrial. 4) Based on technical aspects like three phases, single phase, HT, LT and accuracy class meters.

5.1 Electromechanical induction type Energy meter:

Figure 2. Electro mechanical Induction type Energy meter

It is the common type of watt hour meter which is popularly known and a very old type. It consists of rotating aluminium disc mounted on a spindle between two electromagnets. The Speed of rotation of the disc is directly proportional to the power consumed. This power is integrated by the use of gear trains and counter mechanism. It consists of two magnets one is series electro magnet and other is shunt electro magnet. Series magnet consists of a coil of few turns of thick wire connected in series with line, whereas shunt magnet consists of coil with many turns of thin wire connected across the supply. There exists a

permanent magnet called braking magnet that opposes the rotation of the disc. This makes the disc to be at balanced position and will stop the disc when power is off.

Figure 3. Construction of Electro mechanical Induction type Energy meter

The flux produced by the series magnet is directly proportional to the flow of current and the flux produced by shunt magnet is directly proportional to voltage. Due to the inductive nature the two fluxes are lagged by 90 degrees. Hence it produced a eddy current because of the interaction of these fields in the disk which exerts a forcethat is proportional to the product of instantaneous voltage, current and phase angle between them. The gear arrangement is connected to the vertical spindle or shaft of the aluminium disc that records a number that is equal to the number of revolutions of the disc. This gear arrangement indicates energy consumed over a time. This type of meter is simple in construction but due to creeping and other external fields the accuracy is less. The easy prone to tampering is a major problem with these types of meters which leads to electrical energy monitoring system. These are mostly used in domestic and industrial applications.

5.2 Electronic Energy meters:

Compared to conventional mechanical meters, these are high processed, accurate and reliable type of measuring instruments. These starts measuring instantaneously with less power consumption when connected to load. These meters are in both analog or digital and in analog meters, the power is first converted to proportional frequency or pulse rate and it gets integrated by counters placed inside it. In digital meter a high end processor is used to measure the power directly. To get the energy the power is integrated by logic circuits and also for testing and calibration purpose and later it is then converted to frequency.

5.3 Analog Electronic Energy Meters

In analog type meters, The voltage divider and current transformer gives the voltage and current values respectively when connected to a load. An ADC is used to convert the analog values to digitized samples and using a frequency converter they are again converted to frequency signals.To produce the overall energy consumption these frequency signals are again used to drive the counter mechanism in which these samples are integrated over a certain time period.

Figure 4. Analog type Energy meter working concept

5.4 Digital Electronic Energy Meters

In digital energy meters, digital signal processors or high performance microprocessors are used. Voltage and current transducers are connected to a high resolution ADC which is similar to analog meters. Once it converts analog signals to digital samples, to measure the total power consumed the voltage and current samples are multiplied and integrated by digital circuits [12].

It also calculates reactive power by the use of a microprocessor that measures the phase angle between voltage and current. It is programmed to calculate energy according to the tariff and it also calculates other parameters like power factor, maximum demand, etc. It stores all these values in a non-volatile memory called as EEPROM [13]. For calculating time for power integration, maximum demand and also the date and time stamps for particular parameters, it consists of a real time clock (RTC) which is provided by a battery and other peripherals to backup power. Moreover it interacts with liquid crystal display (LCD), communication devices and other meter outputs.

Figure 5. Circuit diagram of Digital type Energy meter

5.5 Smart Energy Meters

Smart energy meters are advanced metering equipment that involves advanced technology to collect the data, process it and give feedback to the customers from the report made [13]. It measures the amount of energy consumed and remotely operates the switching of supply and controls the maximum usage of electricity. The smart metering system uses intellectual as well as advanced metering infrastructure. These are capable of communicating in both directions. They can transfer the data like energy consumed, values of various parameters, alarms etc to the utilities [14]. They can also receive information such as meter reading, connect/disconnect instructions, upgrading of meter software's and other information from the utilities. The use of humanity is removed for taking the reading of the bill by visiting each house every month. Modems are used in these smart meters to facilitate communication systems such as telephone, wireless, fibre cable, power line communications. The important advantage of smart meter is that it reduces the power theft or the power used in an illegal way, completely by avoiding the tampering of energy meter [15].

Figure 6.Circuit Diagram of Smart Meter

6. Summary

The paper discusses about many different types of energy meters, their construction, development and working. From the above it can be inferred that the existing energy meters are not developed with easy design and has no easy access. The meters are just meant to record and display the readings. It requires human help to read the units and to know about the whole power consumed by a customer which makes the process difficult. Hence in order to overcome all these problems it is necessary to come up with a metering system that should be easy to design and access with low cost. It should be able to transfer the data of power consumption to the customer time to time whenever necessary. Hence we develop a smart metering system which satisfies all the needs and helps the customers to give a customized report. It does not require human interference for taking the readings anymore and is very simple in construction and development.

7. Conclusion

Recent advancement and development in energy meter is discussed in this paper. A lot of recent innovations related to the smart meters and its utilization is reported in the literature. There exists many advancements in the development of metering system from analog meters to smart meters. Internet of Things (IoT) is a recent development in area of technology and can be used along with the energy meters to make them more reliable and smart in nature. Evolution of smart metering systems along with IoT is discussed in literature which is costlier and less user friendly in nature. Hence we come up with the smart metering systems using android application which is the latest development required for the coming generations. These smart metering systems is user friendly that makes a customer to check the power usage at anytime and anywhere from his Android application. It is cost effective and no ready-made software is being used to design and implement. The data is secured and customized as per the needs of the customer.

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